

SOME APPLICATIONS OF RANEY NICKEL TO SYNTHETICAL AND CONSTITUTIONAL PROBLEMS*

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Among the most widely used reduction catalysts is nickel, prepared according to Raney¹ by treating a nickel-aluminium alloy with warm caustic soda solution to dissolve the aluminium. Raney nickel of various grades of activity can be prepared by altering the mode of addition of the alloy, the concentration of the alkaline solution, the temperature and time of digestion, and the intensity of the washing process. These factors were studied in detail by Adkins², who classified the catalysts as W-1, W-2, etc., and standardized their activity in terms of the time and temperature for the reduction of β -naphthol to the two tetrahydro derivatives and the yields of the *ac* and *ar* isomers. The activity of Raney nickel is increased by adding to the alloy in portions caustic soda solution instead of the usual reverse procedure; this catalyst reduces cyclohexanone in ethanol to cyclohexanol at 25° and atmospheric pressure in 22 minutes, while the W-7 catalyst requires 40-50 minutes³.

Raney-nickel reduction may be effected under a wide variety of conditions of temperature, pressure and quantity of catalyst. External hydrogen at pressures varying from atmospheric to 200 atmospheres has been used. Instead of hydrogen itself, hydrazine and other compounds which liberate hydrogen in the presence of the catalyst can be employed⁴. Nitro compounds in alcoholic solution are reduced to amines in good yields by Raney nickel and hydrazine hydrate; by varying the concentration of hydrazine, azoxybenzene and hydrazobenzene can be obtained⁵. Using Raney nickel as a hydrogen transfer agent, reductions have been carried out with the aid of hydrogen donors such as cyclohexanol, as well as oxidations in the presence of hydrogen acceptors such as cyclohexanone; thus benzoin was reduced to dibenzyl or oxidized to benzil⁶. The reported reduction⁶ of 9-anthraldehyde by this method to 9-hydroxymethylanthracene and anthracene needs confirmation because of the susceptibility of the anthracene nucleus to reduction.

Raney-nickel Reduction without External Hydrogen

The ability of Raney nickel to effect reductions (e. g., of ethylenic bonds) in the absence of external hydrogen, utilising the adsorbed hydrogen, was demonstrated by Bougault, Cattelain and Chabrier⁷. They were also the first to show that Raney nickel was valuable as a reagent for the removal of sulphur; thus thioglycollic acid was reduced to acetic acid. The fission of a carbon-carbon bond was found by Snyder and Cannon⁸ to accompany the desulphurization of ethers of ethylenedithiol, methane being formed in addition to ethane.

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The Mozingo Method

Mozingo and his collaborators studied the action of Raney nickel on representative sulphur compounds, such as sulphides, sulphoxides, sulphones and sulphur-containing heterocyclic compounds in view of contemplated investigations of the structure of natural products containing sulphur. Biotin methyl ester was desulphurized by Raney nickel to desthiobiotin methyl ester, hydrolysis of which led to 7:8-diaminopelargonic acid, from which the structure of biotin was deduced⁹. By the action of Raney nickel on an aqueous solution of the sodium salt benzylpenicillin yielded desthiobenzylpenicillin in which the β -lactam ring remained intact; further reduction broke the carbon nitrogen bond of the β -lactam ring and gave *N*-phenylacetyl-L-(+)-alanyl-D(-)-valine. This degradation of penicillin was of great importance since it provided direct evidence for the presence of the β -lactam ring¹⁰.

Reduction or hydrogenolysis by treatment with massive amounts of Raney nickel catalyst in a solvent such as boiling ethanol without the addition of hydrogen has been extensively investigated by Mzingo and his collaborators, and the procedure is therefore referred to in the sequel as the Mzingo method¹¹.

The Schwenk-Papa Method

Whitman, Wintersteiner and Schwenk¹² reduced oestrone to oestradiol (α and β) by treatment with boiling caustic soda solution and Raney (nickel-aluminium) alloy. This technique, which may be termed the Schwenk-Papa method¹³, involves the action of nickel catalyst and hydrogen, both obtained *in situ*¹³. The following are some of the reductions which were effected under these conditions.

Oleic acid	→ Stearic acid
Ph(CH ₂) _x COR	→ Ph(CH ₂) _x -CHOH-R ($x=1$ or more)
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	→ Benzoic acid
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	→ Toluene
Sulphobenzoic acids	→ Benzoic acid
β -(α -Furyl)acrylic acid	→ β -Tetrahydrofurfurylpropionic acid + γ - <i>n</i> -propylbutyrolactone.

An alkoxy group, *o*- or *p*- to a *m*-directing group, was replaced by hydrogen; a *m*-alkoxy was unaffected. Thus *o*- and *p*-methoxybenzoic acids gave a quantitative yield of benzoic acid, and *p*-nitroanisole gave a mixture of aniline (20%) and *p*-anisidine (70%).

Papa, Schwenk and Ginsberg¹⁴ found that β -(α -thenoyl)propionic acid (I) on treatment with Raney alloy in aqueous caustic soda yielded a mixture of about equal parts of γ -ketocaprylic acid (II) and γ -caprylactone (III), or only (II), depending on the ratio of alloy and the reaction time. The higher homologue, ω -(α -thenoyl)pelargonic acid (IV) gave only 10-hydroxymyristic acid (V). Thionaphthenequinone yielded mandelic acid.

In view of the work of Mozingo, Schwenk and others, apart from the work carried out in my laboratory^{15,21}, it is remarkable that Badger, Rodda and Sarse²², who have prepared long-chain fatty acids by the Raney-nickel desulphurization of alkylthienylbutyric acids, have made the statement that "the potentialities of desulphurization as a synthetic method seem to have been largely unrecognized." Similar applications of Raney-nickel desulphurization have also been made by Grey *et al.*²³, Buu-Hoi *et al.*²⁴, and Wynberg and Logothetis²⁵. Naphthalene and phenanthrene derivatives have been synthesized by Raney-nickel desulphurization of appropriate thiophene derivatives²⁶.

Three modifications of Raney nickel were examined by Hurd and Rudner²⁷ in the desulphurization of compounds containing the thiocarbonyl group, thiazoles and thiophenes. Some of the reductions were: *o*-tolylthiourea $\rightarrow$ *o*-toluidine; thio-benzanilide $\rightarrow$ benzylaniline; 2-mercaptobenzothiazole $\rightarrow$ aniline + small amounts of *o*-aminothiophenol and benzothiazole; 2-mercapto-4-phenylthiazole $\rightarrow$ acetophenone; 2-mercapto-4-hydroxythiazole $\rightarrow$ acetaldehyde; 2-acetylthiophene $\rightarrow$ 2-hexanone + small amounts of acetaldehyde and ethanol.

Among other applications of Raney-nickel desulphurization to reactions useful in synthesis may be mentioned the conversion of CO to CH₂ via the thioacetals (diethylmercaptals²⁸; the reduction of phenanthridone to phenanthridine via the thione²⁹; the conversion of cyanuric chloride to *s*-triazine via the trimethylmercapto compound³⁰; the reduction of thioamides to amines³⁰ and to aldehydes³¹; and the conversion of 5-phenyl-2:4-dithiohydantoin into 4-phenylglyoxaline³².

When aromatic mercaptals are treated with Raney nickel from which hydrogen has not been completely removed, binuclear hydrocarbons, such as diphenyl and dibenzyl, are formed³³.

Raney-nickel desulphurization can be effected without change in an asymmetric centre situated at a distance from the sulphur atom³⁴. The enantiomorphic 2-phenyl-2-phenylmercaptopropionamides give racemic 2-phenylpropionamide, but the corresponding sulphones give optically active 2-phenylpropionamides. The two desulphurizations therefore proceed by different mechanisms³⁵. Raney-nickel reduction of 2-methoxy-2-phenylpropionic ester to 2-phenylpropionic ester proceeds with predominant configurational retention, but is not completely stereospecific^{36,37}.

During the course of our studies on the constitution of sulphur dyes, sulphurised vat dyes, thioindigoid dyes and dyes containing sulphonc groups, and in the light

of the earlier work of Mozingo, Schwenk and others, Raney-nickel reductions and desulphurizations appeared to provide a useful mode of attack. In a preliminary investigation¹⁸, it was found that J-acid on treatment with Raney alloy and aqueous caustic soda gave 6-amino-1-naphthol, indicating a method of preparation of relatively inaccessible naphthalene derivatives from readily available dye intermediates; β -naphthol gave a mixture of the *ac* and *ar* tetrahydro compounds; Naphthol AS gave 5:6:7:8-tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthanilide; and carbazole under Mozingo conditions (Raney nickel in boiling ethanol) gave tetrahydrocarbazole.

N-Alkylation

Thiodiphenylamine (VI) on treatment with Raney nickel in boiling ethanol gave diphenylamine; with benzidine-sulphone (VII) desulphurization was accompanied by *N*:*N'*-diethylbenzidine (VIII)¹⁵— a reaction of considerable interest which was subsequently submitted to a more detailed study as a general method of *N*-alkylation¹⁶. Rice and Kohn have described the preparation of *N*:*N'*-diethylbenzidine by this method¹⁹. Mozingo had shown earlier that the action of Raney nickel and boiling ethanol on nitrobenzene, azobenzene and hydrazobenzene led to *N*-ethylaniline¹⁷.

Dehydrothio-*p*-toluidine (IX) in ethanol was degraded by Raney-nickel at room temperature; *N*-ethyl-*p*-toluidine was obtained in nearly 90% yield, apparently by the following mechanism as shown by the fact that benzylaniline gave *N*-ethylaniline.

When equal parts of *p*-toluidine and Raney nickel were refluxed with ethanol, no unreacted *p*-toluidine was detectable after two hours; the sole product was *N*-ethyl-*p*-toluidine (88% yield), and a characteristic feature of the new procedure¹⁶ for *N*-alkylation was that no tertiary amine was formed, and there was no problem of separation of secondary from primary and tertiary amines. It was possible to carry out the reaction at room temperature, but it then required 18 hours to complete.

p-Aminobenzoic acid gave the *N*-ethyl derivative in 70% yield. A steric effect was noticed with *m*-2-xylydine, which was unaffected after 54 hours' refluxing with ethanol in presence of Raney nickel. Methanol did not effect *N*-methylation of aniline or *p*-toluidine, the primary amine having been recovered unchanged. These results support the view⁴⁰ that *N*-alkylation proceeds by the following steps:

n-Propanol, *n*-hexanol and *n*-dodecanol yielded the corresponding secondary amines, but the higher alcohols required progressively longer periods of treatment. *iso*Propanol also reacted with *p*-toluidine to form *N*-*isopropyl-p*-toluidine (48% yield), but prolonged treatment (24 hours) was necessary. With *cyclohexanol* and *p*-toluidine, the interesting observation was made that the expected *N-cyclohexyl-p*-toluidine was accompanied by 4-methyldicyclohexylamine, although the reduction of the benzene nucleus by Raney nickel under such mild conditions was not anticipated. A similar result was obtained with aniline and *cyclohexanol*, the products being *N-cyclohexylaniline* and dicyclohexylamine³⁸.

Alkylation of primary alkylamines was next studied. When *n*-butylamine was treated with Raney nickel in boiling ethanol, no primary amine could be detected after 4 hours. The reaction mixture gave *N*-ethyl-*n*-butylamine and di-*n*-butylamine, together with a very small amount of a product which appeared to be diethylbutylamine. When the reaction was carried out at room temperature for 20 hours, *N*-ethyl-*n*-butylamine and di-*n*-butylamine were again formed. The formation of di-*n*-butylamine in these experiments indicated that in the presence of Raney nickel two molecules of *n*-butylamine reacted with each other. When *n*-butylamine itself was treated with Raney nickel in aqueous solution on a water-bath, di-*n*-butylamine and tri-*n*-butylamine were formed.

When *o*-phenylenediamine was treated with Raney nickel in ethyleneglycol on a boiling water-bath under stirring, the amine could not be detected in the reaction mixture after 14 hours. 1:2:3:4-Tetrahydroquinoxaline was isolated in low yield, together with a liquid containing nitrogen and oxygen which remained to be identified. Although the yield of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinoxaline is low, its synthesis from *o*-phenylenediamine and ethyleneglycol by the action of Raney nickel is of interest as a new application of Raney nickel in organic synthesis and as a new route to 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinoxaline, which may be useful in the preparation of quinoxaline derivatives. Intramolecular cyclizations effected by Raney nickel have been reported by other workers. Catalytic cyclization of 5-amino-2:2:5-trimethyl-3-aza-1-hexanol with Raney nickel gives a 79% yield of 2:2:5:5-tetramethyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyrazine⁴¹. Raney-nickel treatment of $\text{RN}(\text{CH}_2\text{CN})_2$ results in reduction and cyclization to the corresponding piperazine derivative⁴². Dehydrogenation by Raney nickel of an 1:4-diol in boiling benzene leads to the corresponding lactone in excellent yield⁴³.

After our work was completed, Rice and Kohn⁴⁴ and Ainsworth⁴⁵ reported the *N*-alkylation of primary aromatic amines with alcohols and Raney nickel. Rice and Kohn carried out the reaction for longer periods and Ainsworth used larger amounts of Raney nickel. From β -naphthylamine and ethanol Ainsworth obtained only *N*-ethyl- β -naphthylamine, but our experience with naphthalene derivatives has shown that partial hydrogenation of the naphthalene nucleus is difficult to avoid. Rice and Kohn failed to effect *N*-alkylation by isopropanol, but Ainsworth confirmed our observation that prolonged heating resulted in the formation of *N*-isopropylaniline in about 50% yield. Ainsworth found that the reaction of Raney nickel and alcohols with primary aliphatic amines was more complex; 2-phenylethylamine and ethanol gave di-(2-phenylethyl)amine, and benzylamine gave di-benzylamine.

Desulphurization of Thioindigoid Dyes

The action of Raney alloy and aqueous caustic soda at about 100° on thioindigo and its derivatives has led to a new method for the synthesis of diphenacyls, which are otherwise not easy to prepare and which are useful intermediates for cyclization to 2:5-diaryl-furans, pyrroles and thiophenes¹⁶⁻¹⁷. Thioindigo itself gave only a 12% yield of diphenacyl, other products being 1:4-diphenylbutane and benzoic acid; but 6:6'-diethoxythioindigo (X) gave 4:4'-diethoxydiphenacyl (XI) in 80% yield, together with a small amount of *p*-ethoxybenzoic acid. As mentioned earlier, ketones of the type ArCOR yield the hydrocarbon ArCH₂R under the Schwenk-Papa conditions of reduction, and the isolation of diphenacyls from thioindigoid dyes must be explained by poisoning of the nickel catalyst by sulphur after desulphurization has taken place, resulting in the diphenacyls not undergoing further reduction. Since benzoic acids were among the reaction products, the action of Raney alloy and boiling caustic soda solution on acetophenone was examined; benzoic acid was produced. The mechanism by which acetophenone is converted into benzoic acid needs to be investigated.

SOME APPLICATIONS OF RANEY NICKEL

Action of Raney Nickel on Anthraquinone Derivatives

In connection with work on the constitution of dyes, such as Cibacron Yellow R and Orange R, obtained by the thionation of anthraquinone derivatives^{46,47}, the action of Raney alloy and caustic soda solution on anthraquinone, 2-methylanthraquinone, 2-mercaptomethylanthraquinone (XII), bis-2-anthraquinonylmethyl sulphide (XIII) and the corresponding disulphide was studied¹⁸. Anthraquinone gave 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroanthraquinone. When 2-methylanthraquinone was reduced with varying amounts of Raney alloy, several hydrogenation products of 2-methylanthraquinone were obtained. One was 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6-methylanthraquinone, the constitution of which was proved by oxidation to adipic and 4-methylphthalic acids. Desulphurization of (XII) gave 2-methylanthraquinone, 2-hydroxymethylanthraquinone and anthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid; (XIII) gave 2-methylanthraquinone and traces of anthraflavone (XIV); and the disulphide gave 2-methylanthraquinone, 2-hydroxymethylanthraquinone and anthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid. Anthraflavone gave decahydroanthraflavone as the major product and a small amount of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6-methylanthraquinone, the latter being formed by fission of the ethylenic bond.

Synthesis of γ -Resorcylic Acid

In 1949 Kenner and Murray⁴⁸ described an interesting method for the reduction of phenol to benzene via the tosylate (*p*-toluenesulphonate), which underwent hydrogenolysis when an alcoholic solution was treated with Raney nickel and hydrogen at atmospheric pressure and room temperature:

m-Acetamidophenol was thus reduced to acetanilide (90%), and methyl salicylate to methyl benzoate (80%); β -naphthol led to tetralin, the naphthalene ring undergoing further hydrogenation. We have used the Kenner-Murray reduction for a variety of

synthetical purposes. It provided, for instance, a new and convenient route to γ -resorcylic acid (XV), in the sodium salt of which there was a passing interest as a therapeutic agent in rheumatic fever for which advantages were claimed in comparison with sodium salicylate; (XV) was prepared in an overall yield of about 75% from phloroglucinol by carboxylation, mono-*O*-tosylation to form (XVI), and final hydrogenolysis of the potassium salt under the Murray-Kenner conditions.

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII)

Vanillic acid was similarly converted, via the tosylate, into *m*-methoxybenzoic acid; but the yield was only 30% (increased to 65% by reduction under the Mazingo conditions), the methoxyl *ortho* to the tosylate group having an unfavourable effect. Two adjacent methoxyls inhibited the reduction so that the procedure was not available for the preparation of 3:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid from syringic acid. Seshadri⁴⁹ has used the method for the preparation of the biogenetically important 6 methylsalicylic acid from orsellinic acid. V. Ramanathan⁵⁰ found that the Mazingo reduction of vanillin tosylate (XVII) gave *m*-cresylmethyl ether (60%), while the Murray-Kenner reduction gave *m*-methoxybenzyl alcohol (80% yield).

(XVIII)

(XX)

Synthesis of 5-Hydroxyflavones

Removal of a phenolic hydroxyl group by hydrogenolysis of the tosylate has proved to be useful in the flavone and xanthone series^{50, 50}. Chrysin (5:7-dihydroxyflavone) has been converted into 5-hydroxyflavone, and galangin-3-methyl ether (5:7 dihydroxy-3-methoxyflavone) to 5-hydroxy-3-methoxyflavone. A general method has thus become available for the synthesis of 5-hydroxyflavones, which are of interest because of their possible occurrence in nature and also as intermediates for the synthesis of naturally occurring 5:8-dihydroxyflavones by the Elbs-Seshadri persulphate oxidation. Chrysin and galangin-3-methyl ether readily gave the 7-tosyl ester (XVIII) and (XIX) on treatment with a molar proportion of tosyl chloride and excess of anhydrous potassium carbonate in boiling acetone. It was necessary to carry out the hydrogenolysis of the tosyl derivatives under controlled and mild conditions, leaving

a part of the tosyl derivative unchanged to poison the nickel catalyst in order to avoid undesirable side reactions. The crude reaction mixture was treated with alcoholic caustic potash to hydrolyse the unchanged tosyl derivative, and the mixture of hydroxyflavones separated by chromatography. Thus, by the hydrogenolysis of the 7-tosyl ester (XVIII) of chrysin, a mixture of 5-hydroxyflavone (XX) and chrysin was obtained; when the mixed flavones were dissolved in benzene and chromatographed on Florex xxx (an extruded fuller's earth supplied by the Floridin Co., Inc.), development and elution with benzene yielded 5-hydroxyflavone (XX) in a yield of about 25% calculated on the quantity of the tosyl derivative (XVIII) consumed in the reaction. Elution with ethyl acetate then led to the recovery of the more strongly adsorbed chrysin. The 7-tosyl ester (XIX) of galangin-3-methyl ether on Raney-nickel treatment and hydrolysis of the product yielded galangin-3-methyl ether and 5-hydroxy-3-methoxyflavone (XXI), readily separable by chromatography. Galangin-3-methyl ether and 5-hydroxy-3-methoxyflavone can also be separated by taking advantage of the sparing solubility of the former in benzene.

Kurth and Hubbard⁵¹ isolated from *Ponderosa* pine bark a bright yellow colouring matter, to which they assigned the structure 3:5:8:3':4'-pentahydroxyflavone (XXII) which was synthesised by the indicated route, and found to be different in its m.p. and other properties from the *Ponderosa* colouring matter²¹. Further work has shown that the latter is a complex mixture, from which quercetin, taxifolin (2:3-dihydroquercetin), and two new colouring matters, 6-methylquercetin (pinoquercetin) and 6-methylmyricetin (pinomyricetin) have so far been isolated⁵².

A New General Method for the Reduction of Quinones to the corresponding Hydrocarbon Derivatives

The action of Raney nickel on the sulphuric esters of phenols has been studied to determine if sulphuric esters can be used as intermediates in place of tosyl esters for the removal of phenolic hydroxyl groups⁵³. *p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid

was sulphated using pyridine and chlorosulphonic acid. The sulphuric ester was not isolated, but converted into the dipotassium salt (XXIII), which was treated with Raney nickel and hydrogen. From the reaction mixture benzoic acid (65%) and a little *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid were isolated.

The hydrogenolysis of (XXIV), the disodium salt of the disulphuric ester of anthrahydroquinone, was then examined. An aqueous solution of the disulphuric ester was treated with Raney nickel and hydrogen for 4 hours at room temperature and filtered. Benzene extraction of the nickel residue after deactivation gave a mixture of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroanthraquinone and hydrogenated anthracene; the latter was then dehydrogenated by selenium to anthracene in an overall yield of 30%. From the aqueous filtrate, after oxidation with sodium nitrite and sulphuric acid, a further quantity of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroanthraquinone was recovered, indicating that hydrogenation of anthrahydroquinone disulphuric ester to 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroanthrahydroquinone disulphuric ester also took place as a side reaction. The formation of a quinonoid derivative, because of the incomplete hydrogenolysis of the ester even when a large amount of Raney nickel was used, was practically eliminated by carrying out the reaction using Raney alloy and aqueous alkali instead of Raney-nickel catalyst. This modification gave an excellent yield of hydrogenated anthracene (85%) which could be readily dehydrogenated to anthracene.

(XXIII)

(XXIV)

A new general method for the conversion of quinones to the corresponding hydrocarbons through the disulphuric esters of the leuco derivatives thus became available^{5a}. The cleavage of sulphuric esters by Raney nickel affords an alternative route for the preparation of hydrocarbons, having advantages over phosphorus-hydriodic acid and zinc dust distillation methods, which use high temperatures and may cause structural rearrangement. Sulphuric esters of leuco derivatives of over thirty vat dyes are available commercially and numerous analogues can be readily prepared, providing suitable raw materials for the preparation of polycyclic hydrocarbons, azahydrocarbons, etc., which are of interest in connection with their chemical reactivity, electronic structure, absorption spectra, photochemical behaviour and carcinogenic properties.

Dibenzopyrenes

Reduction of Indigosol Golden Yellow IGK (XXVI), the disodium salt of the disulphuric ester of Indanthrene Golden Yellow GK (3:4:8:9-dibenzopyrene-5:10-quinone, XXV), by means of Raney alloy and aqueous alkali afforded an excellent

yield (80%) of a mixture of hydrogenated hydrocarbons, which were separated by chromatography into hexahydrodibenzpyrene (m.p. 240-41°) and decahydrodibenzpyrene (m. p. 235-36°). By treatment with iodine and sodium acetate in boiling nitrobenzene, the mixture of hydrogenated hydrocarbons was dehydrogenated to 3:4:8:9-dibenzpyrene (XXVII), prepared earlier by other workers from the quinone (XXV) by zinc dust distillation, Clar reduction, and reduction with phosphorus and hydriodic acid.

(XXV)

(XXVI)

(XXVII)

For determining the constitution of commercial anthraquinonoid vat dyes, the Raney-nickel hydrogenolysis of their leuco sulphuric esters is sometimes a useful approach. One example is Mayvat Brilliant Red AF, recently marketed in the United States as an "entirely new homogeneous anthraquinone vat colour". A preliminary examination of the dye, which crystallised from *o*-dichlorobenzene in red needles, showed that it was a halogenated quinone containing chlorine and bromine, but no nitrogen or sulphur. The leuco sulphuric ester was prepared by the usual Seldon process⁵⁴ and reduced with Raney alloy and caustic soda solution. The product was a mixture of hydroaromatic compounds, dehydrogenation of which with selenium led to 3:4:9:10-dibenzpyrene (XXVIII), identified by its m.p. and absorption spectrum⁵⁵. On shaking Mayvat Brilliant Red AF with caustic soda solution and hydrogen in presence of a catalytic amount of Raney nickel, dehalogenation took place, and the product after crystallisation was identified as 3:4:9:10-dibenzpyrene-5:8-quinone (XXIX). Mayvat Brilliant Red AF therefore proved to be a chloro-bromo derivative of the quinone (XXIX), and this dye is a very convenient source for the hydrocarbon (XXVIII), which is currently of interest because of its powerful carcinogenic properties⁵⁶. Indanthrene Scarlet 4G has been stated⁵⁷ to be the dibromo derivative of (XXIX), but a sample kindly supplied by Cassella Farbwerke, Mainkur, has been found to contain both chlorine and bromine. Dehalogenation yielded the quinone

(XXIX). Indanthrene Scarlet 4G and Mayvat Brilliant Red AF dye have substantially different shades and they exhibit different colours in sulphuric acid; the number and position of the halogen atoms, which must be responsible for these differences, are under investigation. The quinone (XXIX) can be reduced to the hydrocarbon (XXVIII) smoothly and in excellent yield by means of aluminium *cyclohexoxide* in boiling *cyclohexanol*, which Coffey and Boyd have shown to be effective for reducing anthraquinone to anthracene and anthanthrone to anthanthrene⁵⁹.

(XXIX)

(XXVIII)

16:17-Dimethoxyviolanthrene

A quinone which can be reduced to the corresponding hydrocarbon derivative by aluminium *cyclohexoxide* in *cyclohexanol* is the important dye 16:17-dimethoxyviolanthrone (Caledon Jade Green; XXX). Alternatively, when the disulphuric ester of the leuco compound, available commercially, was treated with Raney alloy, aqueous caustic soda and toluene under specified conditions, a 50 % yield of 16:17-dimethoxyviolanthrene (XXXI) was obtained⁶⁰. A notable feature of this hydrogenolysis was that, unlike the other reductions of the sulphuric esters of quinones which gave the hydrogenated hydrocarbons, the direct product of the Raney-nickel reduction was the aromatic compound (XXXI) and not a partially hydrogenated derivative. The new compound (XXXI) is of very special interest since it is an "overcrowded molecule" which is optically active and can be resolved by using the new technique of Newman⁶⁰ in which the complex with optically active 2-(2:4:5:7-tetranitro-9-fluorenylideneaminooxy)-propionic acid is fractionally crystallised. The stereochemistry of Caledon Jade Green (XXX) in relation to its colour has been discussed elsewhere⁶¹.

(XXX)

(XXXI)

Synthesis of 1-Azanaphthacene

A further application of the Raney-nickel method for the reduction of quinones to the corresponding hydrocarbon derivatives is the synthesis of the hitherto unknown 1-azanaphthacene (XXXII)²³. The Skraup reaction on 2-amino-1-chloro-anthraquinone, adding arsenic pentoxide to suppress the benzanthrone reaction, gave a good yield of 12-chloro-1-azanaphthacene-6:11-dione (XXXIII). Dechlorination by means of caustic soda and sodium hydrosulphite and air oxidation of the vat yielded 1-azanaphthacene-6:11-dione (XXXIV). Treatment of the disodium salt (XXXV) of the disulphuric ester of (XXX) with Raney alloy and caustic soda at 100° gave an octahydroazanaphthacene, the absorption spectrum of which showed that it had the structure (XXXVI), and which was dehydrogenated to 1-azanaphthacene (XXXII) by prolonged heating with palladized carbon in boiling Dowtherm.

Synthesis of Benzanthracenes

The hydrogenolysis of leuco sulphuric esters of quinones by Raney alloy and aqueous alkali to the corresponding hydrocarbon derivatives has been extended to the leuco sulphuric esters of 1:2-benzanthraquinone and its derivatives for the preparation of benzanthracene and methylbenzanthracenes²⁴, which are of interest in connection with their carcinogenic activity and which were synthesized earlier in poor yields by much more difficult routes. Thus, the hydrogenolysis of the sulphuric ester of benzanthrahydroquinone gave a hydrogenated benzanthracene, which was dehydrogenated to 1:2-benzanthracene (XXXVII) in an overall yield of 70%.

(XXXVII)

(XXXVIII)

(XXXIX)

The Friedel-Crafts condensation of 1-chloro-2-methylnaphthalene with phthalic anhydride took place in the 5-position, and cyclization with sulphuric acid gave 4'-chloro-3'-methyl-1:2-benzanthraquinone (XXXVIII), which was reduced to 3'-methylbenzanthracene (XXXIX) by treatment of the leuco sulphuric ester with Raney alloy and caustic soda solution, followed by dehydrogenation with 2:3-dichloro-5:6-dicyanobenzoquinone⁵³.

(XLII)

(XLI)

(XL)

The synthesis of 4-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene (XL) was achieved through the trisodium salt (XLI) of the trisulphuric ester of leuco 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzanthraquinone. The desired benzanthraquinone derivative, 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzanthraquinone (XLII), was obtained by condensing 3-hydroxybenzanthraquinone with aqueous caustic soda, sodium hydrosulphite and formaldehyde (the Marschalk reaction)⁵⁴. The intermediate 3-hydroxybenzanthraquinone was prepared by a slight modification of Fieser's method⁵⁵. As a pilot experiment, the trisulphuric ester of leuco 2-hydroxyanthraquinone was reduced by Raney alloy and aqueous caustic soda to a hydrogenated anthracene, which was then dehydrogenated to anthracene, showing that nuclear hydroxyl groups in the anthraquinone series could be reduced via the sulphuric ester. The reduction of the trisulphuric ester (XLI) of leuco 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzanthraquinone similarly gave a hydrocarbon, analysing for a hexahydro-4-methylbenzanthracene which was dehydrogenated to 4-methylbenzanthracene (XL) by boiling in benzene with dichlorodicyanobenzoquinone.

Raney-nickel reduction has proved valuable in dealing with the problem of the

constitution of morellin, the main colouring matter of the seeds of *Garcinia morella*. On the basis of a new formula, $C_{23}H_{30}O_7$, selective hydrogenation, alkaline hydrolysis, and ultraviolet and infra-red absorption data, a partial structure for morellin was suggested earlier⁶. Evidence for a 2:2-dimethylchromene ring and a 5-hydroxy-chromanone ring, built on a phloroglucinol nucleus, was conclusive. The chromanone ring was considered to be part of a partially hydrogenated 1:2-benzoxanthone ring system. The disposition of the ethylenic bonds and a second carbonyl group in the naphthalene moiety remains uncertain, but definite evidence for the presence of a partially hydrogenated naphthalene ring has been obtained by the use of Raney nickel. The action of Raney nickel in boiling cyclohexanol on morellin gave a product (A), m.p. 172°, which was also produced by an attempted palladium-charcoal dehydrogenation of the Raney-nickel reduction product, m. p. 110-11°, described earlier. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of (A) closely resembled the spectra of dihydrotoxicarol and hexahydro-osajin. When (A) was fused with caustic potash at 290°, two of the products were *n*-valeric acid and an acid (B), m.p. 281°, which analysed for $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$, a tetrahydronaphthalene dicarboxylic acid. Treatment of (B) with copper-bronze and quinoline with the object of effecting decarboxylation resulted in simultaneous dehydrogenation with the formation of naphthalene. The utility of copper in boiling quinoline as a reagent for dehydrogenation was demonstrated by the conversion of tetrahydronaphthalene to naphthalene. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of the acid (B) in comparison with the spectra of benzoic acid and the three phthalic acids, and the fact that nitric acid oxidation of (B) yielded mellophanic acid (benzene-1:2:3:5-tetracarboxylic acid), showed that (B) was tetrahydronaphthalene-5:7-dicarboxylic acid.

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